

Deliverable D-JRP- TOXOSOURCES-WP5.1

SOP for a novel NGS-MLST genotyping method of WP5 Work package 5 of JRP22-FBZ4.1- TOXOSOURCES

Responsible Partners:
FLI, ISS, UCM, SSI

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D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5.1

SOP FOR

A NOVEL NGS-MLST GENOTYPING METHOD OF WP5

BACKGROUND

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-toxosources/>);

Work Package:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5 Novel *Toxoplasma gondii* typing method to detect within-genotype variation;

Task:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5-T2 Novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST *Toxoplasma gondii* genotyping method.

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TOXOSOURCES addresses the research question – **What are the relative contributions of the different sources of *T. gondii* infection?** – by using several multidisciplinary approaches and novel and improved methods to yield robust estimates that can inform risk management and policy makers.

TOXOSOURCES WP5 aims to identify highly polymorphic regions in genomes of very closely related *T. gondii* strains across Europe. Preliminary NGS data on European type II *T. gondii* revealed substantial variation between isolates and relative to reference strains. Using a panel of representative strains, regions in the genome with a higher SNP density are identified and used to establish a novel high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST-typing method. Objectives of TOXOSOURCES WP5:

- ✓ To develop a novel *T. gondii* typing method with the discriminatory power needed in Europe
- ✓ To apply the novel method in pilot studies

This deliverable reports on the work to establish a standard operating procedure (SOP) to be implemented among consortium partners and to be applied in pilot studies.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK AND EVALUATION OF THE KEY STEPS OF THE METHOD

Reference isolates and other positive samples

A large number of reference *T. gondii* isolates, WGS-quality DNA samples or WGS-data on isolates were collected from across Europe. Isolates were expanded in-vitro, and DNA was extracted for WGS. The focus was on *T. gondii* type II isolates, while a selection of other isolates like type II x III recombinant and exotic strains were included as well.

In addition, *T. gondii* positive field samples (among them histological blocks or native tissues of infected intermediate hosts, fecal samples of definitive hosts) were collected for validating of the novel high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method.

A higher number of isolates and DNAs than originally planned proved highly useful for the work. The collected *T. gondii* isolates and DNA samples were not only useful to establish the method but are applied for refinement of the method. The collection also provides the base for inter-laboratory comparison and pilot studies.

Characterization using standard techniques

The DNA samples in the panel were characterized using current state-of-the-art methods, including a TaqMan real time qPCR-based quantification of *T. gondii* DNA and typing by a PCR-RFLP- and a microsatellite-based typing.

Selection of potentially suitable target regions

In a first approach the whole genome data per isolate (65 Mbps, n=40, European *T. gondii* type II) were screened for loci in which a sufficient number of SNPs is located, probable suitable to differentiate *T. gondii* type II isolates. In total 865 loci were identified on 14 chromosomes with 5-35 SNPs per 333 bp (19, 20-35 SNPs; 37, 15-19 SNPs; 136, 10-14 SNPs; 673, 5-9 SNPs). Out of these, 55 were shortlisted and sequence differences and SNPs confirmed by Sanger sequencing. Finally, 18 loci (SNP-rich regions) on 11 chromosomes were selected.

Establishing a multiplex PCR to amplify 18 SNP-rich regions

Using Ion AmpliSeq Designer (v7.4.11, © 2020 Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, United States) two primer panels were established, designed to amplify important parts of 18 SNP-rich regions. Each of the two panels addressed all 18 SNP-rich regions.

Assessing the number and size of SNP-rich regions amplified by multiplex PCR

Using these two primer panels, a set of nine genetically different *T. gondii* type II isolates (including reference isolate Me49) were selected and multiplex PCRs (n=24 cycles) performed using the DNA template concentration (Ct 17-21) and the annealing temperature (60°C) recommended in supplied kits.

After library preparation, purification, size selection and quality control on a high sensitivity chip on a Bioanalyzer instrument, the libraries were quantified and the sequencing templates prepared. Sequencing was performed on an IonS5 sequencer aiming at 200.000 reads per library.

In this wet-lab experiment all 18 SNP-rich regions were covered in case of all nine genetically different *T. gondii* type II DNA samples. In one SNP-rich region, results were hard to assess because this region covered a tandemly repeated sequence, previously not noticed. This region was excluded from further evaluation. In two other SNP-rich regions, parts of the regions were covered by a lower number of sequencing reads compared to the rest of the regions.

In-silico assessment of the novel typing-tool based on 17 SNP-rich targets

In-silico analyses using whole genome sequencing data on 60 isolates and knowledge on the 17 SNP-rich sequence regions covered in the wet-lab experiment revealed for 51 of 60 European type II isolates included different typing patterns. Only DNA samples of *T. gondii* isolated in the same outbreak or representing different definitive-host cyclic passages of the same isolate revealed identical typing patterns. By comparison, microsatellite typing, representing the current reference standard, was able to discriminate 49 of the 60 type II strains.

Furthermore, the in-silico analysis revealed that typing patterns of DNA samples of type I and type III isolates as well as type II x III recombinant strains and exotic strains were clearly separated from each other and those of type II isolates.

Assessing the effect of changing cycle conditions (number of cycles, annealing temperature)

Using reference type II DNA, further wet-lab experiments are performed to find optimal cycling conditions.

Assessing the required *T. gondii* DNA concentration in field samples

Using reference type II DNA, further wet-lab experiments are performed to define *T. gondii* DNA concentrations at which typing can be achieved. In addition, field samples (DNA from various tissues, DNA from fecal samples, etc.) are used to assess the effect of quality and origin of sample DNA.

Discussion on practical challenges on taking new technology in use and possible solutions

As with all new methods, there are practical challenges in taking it to use in laboratories. Discussion on these will be taken up e.g. in a Dissemination Workshop organized by overarching WP5 of One Health EJP.

FINAL STEPS

A standardized workflow for the collection and preliminary analysis of NGS-MLST data on *T. gondii* is being established. The new technology is distributed to interested partners by a physical workshop at FLI or - due to COVID-19 situation - as an online workshop.

References

Ion AmpliSeq Library Kit Plus User Guide
Ion 510 & Ion 520 & Ion 530 Kit – Chef USER GUIDE

Acknowledgements

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